

Linked Micromap Plots using the micromapST R Package

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Abstract

Linked micromap plots display geospatial data on small maps linked by color to statistical graphics, enabling the user to explore and to communicate the underlying patterns in the data. Sorting by a statistical column can reveal geospatial clusters of similar values or correlations between the columns. We designed the R package micromapST to produce publishable quality linked micromap plots with minimal user input. Although the first version only displayed U.S. maps at the state level, subsequent versions can display data for other geographic units. The new version allows users to supply their own geographic boundary file so that linked micromaps can be produced for virtually any geospatial structure. Also, new types of glyphs and user options have been added. We will describe linked micromap plots and demonstrate how to use the latest version of micromapST to produce them.

Key Words: data visualization, spatial data, maps

1. Linked micromaps – History and definition

Dan Carr of George Mason University created the linked micromap design while consulting with Tony Olsen’s group at the EPA. Dan suggested a sorted row plot (Figure 1) to easily compare pollutant levels place to place. Tony asked if there was some way to show where these places were, leading Dan to add a column of small maps to the rowplot, thus creating linked micromap plots.

Figure 1: Sorted row-labeled plots (cropped) (Carr, 1994)

As shown in the simple example in Figure 2, each row in a linked micromap plot represents a place, just as in the rowplots. The rows are grouped into “perceptual groups” to ease the cognitive burden on the user. You only need to compare the statistical values and spatial patterns of the areas within a group, here four states. Note that color only serves to link the state name, glyph and map location – it does NOT represent a value as it would on a choropleth map. An additional advantage of the perceptual grouping is that we can reuse the colors for each group, allowing us to use just a few very saturated colors that are easy to distinguish from each other.

This simple example has three columns for each row: from left to right, the state name, the statistical glyph, and a small map. Only the states in this perceptual group are shaded in that group’s map. You can see in this small example how the maps identify spatial clusters based on the sorted values. In addition to perceptual grouping of rows, other design elements are based on past cognitive research:

- Humans are good at judging length, so we use a common axis at the bottom.

White Male All Cancer Mortality Rates, 2018-2022

Figure 2: A basic linked micromap plot of 12 midwestern U.S. states

- Sorting helps with comparisons, putting places with similar values close to each other.
- White gridlines help guide the eye across the rows to the glyphs and down the columns to the axis.
- Saturated, very distinct hues are easy to distinguish on the maps

2. The micromapST R package

2.1 Package History and Development

Linked micromaps were first implemented in SPlus. Then the National Cancer Institute, with Dan Carr's guidance, implemented an online linked micromap application in JAVA. This was good for communicating cancer data to the public, but the user couldn't change much about the display or use their own data or geographic areas.

When we converted these early programs to R (R Core Team, 2024), we wanted to make it easily portable and modifiable and to allow user input. We also wanted the default output to be of publishable quality, while still allowing optional format changes, so that even the user with minimal R coding skills could get a reasonable looking linked micromap plot. We also decided to rely on the most basic R functions as much as possible, rather than calling another mapping package, to speed up execution. This is important if you are running the package repeatedly for exploratory analyses.

Unfortunately, we named the package micromapST, because it only processed US states at the beginning, but over the years other geographic boundary files have been added and now you can read in your own boundary file to create a micromap. The examples in this article will illustrate most of the statistical glyphs available in micromapST.

2.2 Calling the Package

It takes four steps to create a linked micromap using micromapST (Pickle, Pearson, Carr 2015). You first load the package from CRAN (<https://CRAN.R-project.org/>), then read in your data (however you need to do that). You need enough knowledge of R coding to do these steps, but they are only done once. Then you define the structure and content of the linked micromap in a data frame (called panelDesc in these examples), and then call the function to create the plot. Here is the R code for these two steps (set off by "####"):

```

### describe columns, left to right
panelDesc <- data.frame(
  type=c("map","id","dot","dot"),
  coll=c(NA, NA, "Rate90","EverSmkF"),
  lab1=c(NA, NA, "Rates 1990s",
        "Ever Smoked F %")
)
micromapST(FSCdata,panelDesc,
  rowNames="ab",
  rowNamesCol="StAbbrev",
  sortVar="Rate90",ascend=FALSE
)
###

```

The panel description dataframe, called panelDesc in this example, describes what you want your linked micromap to look like. Because we want four columns of output, every one of the specifications in panelDesc MUST have four columns. We use NA as a placeholder if nothing is needed.

The parameter “type” specifies four columns, left to right: maps, a place identifier and two dot plots. The parameter “coll” defines the column names in the input dataframe that will provide the data for these four columns. Because the map and area identifier are built into the package, these are shown as NA, followed by the two variables to be plotted as dots. Similarly, “lab1” provides the labels for the four output columns. Again, the maps and identifiers have standard labels, so we don’t need to provide them.

Figure 3: Results of R code (left) to call micromapST

Now that we have specified the output format for the linked micromap, we can call the function to create the graphic. The minimum that we need to provide is two dataframe names – one for the input data and one for the output graphic’s description. Here we have also specified that the state i.d. will be shown as the postal abbreviation and that the micromap rows will be sorted by the variable Rate90 in descending order. The output is shown in Figure 3. Since the default size of each perceptual group is 5, we have 10 small maps displayed for the 50 US states.

3. Exploring a Covid Dataset

3.1 Background

To demonstrate the usefulness of the linked micromap design for data exploration, we will investigate a covid dataset. Our input data consists of the cumulative number of covid cases reported to each state for each month from February 2020 to April 2022. In order to put these numbers on roughly the same scale for comparisons, we divided each number by the 2019 state population.

Some questions we would like to explore are:

- Where are rates particularly high?
- Were there differences in the timing of covid surges by state or region?

- Were the observed patterns associated with state differences in personal behaviors, e.g., mask wearing (data from a Facebook survey conducted by Carnegie Mellon; Salomon et al., 2021).

Can linked micromap plots help us in this exploration?

3.2 Default Linked Micromap Plot

A series of linked micromap plots using `micromapST` can address these questions. For each variation, the revised R code will illustrate how little the initial code needs to be changed to get very different looking plots.

The first example is the simplest, using default values. We want three columns: maps, state identifier, and a dot plot (“type”) of the cumulative case rate on November 20, 2020, (“col1”) labeled “Cases/1000” (“lab1”). The function call provides the name of the input dataframe and the dataframe we just set up describing the micromap structure, plus an optional title. As shown in Figure 4, there is no discernible pattern either on the maps or in the dot column because the default sort order is alphabetic by state identifier.

```
### READ IN DATA
st_covid_case_rates <- read.csv("data/STCaseRatesPer1000.csv", row.names = 2)

# DEFINE LINKED MICROMAP STRUCTURE
panel_desc_covid1 <- data.frame(
  type = c("map", "id", "dot"),
  col1 = c(NA, NA, "Nov_20_2020"),
  lab1 = c("", "", "Cases/1000")
)
# CALL FUNCTION
micromapST(
  statsDFrame = st_covid_case_rates,
  panelDesc = panel_desc_covid1,
  title = c("US State Covid Cumulative Case Rates per 1000 Population, Nov. 20, 2020")
)
###
```

3.3 Adding Options to Explore the Spatio-temporal Data

To specify a sorting variable and a descending order sort, add

```
sortVar = "Nov_20_2020", ascend = FALSE,
```

to the function call. Note that since the micromap structure hasn’t changed, we don’t have to respecify the `panelDesc`. Just by sorting, we can see in Figure 5 that there are several states (ND, SD) with much higher cumulative case rates in November 2020 (dot plot) and that the top 5 states are clustered geographically around the Dakotas (ND, SD).

These micromaps showed only one time point but we have over two years of monthly cumulative counts. Let’s look at the entire time series. Now we change the statistical column type to “ts” for time series and add several more labels. Label 3 (“lab3”) will print at the bottom. We need another line in `panelDesc` to specify the array that holds the time series values for each state. The call to `micromapST` is the same except now we sort on the midpoint value of the time series. (New or modified code is shown in bold.)

```
###
panel_desc_timeseries <- data.frame(
  type = c("map", "id", "ts"),
  lab1 = c("", "", "Cases/1000"),
```

```

lab2 = c("", "", "Feb 2020-Apr 2022"),
lab3 = c("", "", "Month-Year"),
panelData = c(NA, NA, "temp_array2")
)

micromapST( statsDFrame = temp_rates,
  panelDesc = panel_desc_timeseries,
  sortVar = "Mar_20_2021", ascend = FALSE,
  title = c("Cumulative covid rates, Feb 2020 - Apr 2022")
)
###

```


Figure 4: U.S. state covid cumulative case rates per 100,000 population, Nov. 20, 2020, sorted by state abbreviation

Figure 5: U.S. state covid cumulative case rates per 100,000 population, Nov. 20, 2020, sorted by case rate in descending order

The result is shown in Figure 6, zoomed in to the top half of states for a closer look. Comparing overlapping time series lines is more difficult than comparing single dots. There is a lot of information here, but perceptual grouping means that we only need to examine 5 state lines at a time. The top 5 states are a little different here because we are sorting on March 2021 values, not November 2020 as before. However, ND and SD are still the highest and we can see here that they had a surge in the fall of 2020, earlier than other states.

Cumulative covid rates, Feb 2020-Apr 2022

Covid Rates: States trend arrows and county boxplots

Figure 6: Time series plots for covid rates

Figure 7: Arrow plot of covid case rates and box plots of county case rates

One last type of display for time series data is an arrow plot. Here we specify an arrow plot in the panel description. The endpoints of the arrow are defined in “col1” and “col2”. We also would like to drill down to the county level in each state to judge how much spread there is within each state. For that, we create a boxplot 5-value summary for each state outside the package, then “panelData” specifies the name of the boxplot information needed for its display in column four. We still want to sort by the midpoint date value, so nothing needs to be changed in the micromapST call.

```
###
panel_desc_arrow_boxplot <- data.frame(
  type = c("map", "id", "arrow", "boxplot"),
  lab1 = c("", "", "State rates", "County rates Apr 22"),
  lab2 = c("", "", "Trend Feb 20-Mar 21", "(suppressed if 1-9 )"),
  lab3 = c("", "", "Cases/1000", "Cases/1000"),
  col1 = c(NA, NA, "Feb_24_2020", NA),
  col2 = c(NA, NA, "Mar_20_2021", NA),
  panelData = c("", "", "", "covid_box_list")
)
###
```

Zooming in again to the top half of states, Figure 7 shows that ND and SD still had the highest cumulative case rates at the midpoint of the time series. Most of the states had a pretty narrow distribution of county rates, but a few extreme outliers affect the scaling of the entire boxplot column. Now that we have explored the time series of rates, can we discover any interesting associations with possible risk factors?

The Facebook survey on covid behaviors included the question “In the past week, did you usually wear a mask when you were outside your home?” We will use those results from September 2020 and display the percents as dots with standard errors (“dotse”). The “col1” and “col2” lines give the names of the dot and standard error variables, respectively. Other design changes requested by this code are: cumulative map shading (“mapcum”), a reference line in the fourth column (mask wearing %) with value 85 and label “US %”, and in the function call we ask that the states be labeled with full names.

```
###
panel_desc_covid2 <- data.frame(
  type = c("mapcum", "id", "dot", "dotse"),
```

```

lab1 = c("", "", "Cases/1000", "% wore mask"),
col1 = c(NA, NA, "Nov_20_2020", "PctWoreMask0920"),
col2 = c(NA, NA, NA, "PctMaskStderr"),
refVals = c(NA, NA, NA, 85),
refTexts = c(NA, NA, NA, "US %")
)
micromapST( statsDFrame = st_covid_case_rates,
  panelDesc = panel_desc_covid2,
  sortVar = "Nov_20_2020", ascend = FALSE,
  plotNames = "full",
  title = c("US State Covid Cumulative Case Rates, Nov. 20, 2020,",
    " and percent who usually wore a mask, Sep 2020")
)
###

```

In Figure 8, the cumulative map option colors the states that were shaded in the maps above in light yellow. For example, the second map down highlights states ranked 6-10 in the usual colors, but states ranked 1-5 in the top map are shaded light yellow in the second map. By reading the maps top to bottom, we can see a growing cluster of high rate states in the north central region.

Full state names instead of abbreviations are shown in column two. Error bars are shown around the dots. The US reference line for mask wearing is a dashed vertical green line. In general, we see an inverted V shape indicating a negative correlation between covid rates and mask wearing.

Putting these observations together we can conclude that high cumulative covid rates were clustered in the north central states, particularly ND and SD, in late 2020 and that these high rates seem negatively correlated with mask wearing. These results are consistent with an epidemiologic study that found that a motorcycle rally with 460,000 attendees in Sturgis SD in August 2020 was a covid superspreader event, causing many subsequent cases in Minnesota (Firestone 2020). The linked micromap plots showed that rates in other nearby states also rose after many of the attendees returned home there. Most of the attendees were said to be strongly against wearing masks and South Dakota did not have any policy requiring their use. This example shows the power of linked micromaps to explore geographic patterns and associations among several variables.

4. Other Available Glyphs in micromapST

4.1 Segmented Bar Charts

Leaving the covid data, there are two more types of graphics micromapST can produce. Figure 9 displays a segmented bar chart useful for categorical response data. The bars in this example represent four categories of Math Proficiency by state, reported as percent of 8th grade students in 2011 who scored Less Than Basic, Basic, Proficient and Advanced (U.S. Department of Education, 2011). All four values for each state are displayed as light to full saturation of the hue for that state, e.g., DC on the first row is shaded red on the map and in the i.d. column. Its four bars are shaded light to darker red from left to right, representing Less Than Basic through Advanced, respectively.

These bars are centered at the division between Basic and Proficient. Centering allows the user to judge the length of the bar to the left and right of center (Heiberger and Robbins, 2014), that is, Less Than Proficient to the left and At Least Proficient to the right. (Remember that we are good at judging lengths.) One observation from this plot is that although DC has the largest percentage of students who tested Less Than Basic level (lightest segment), its percent Less Than Proficient (the length of the bar to the left of center) is not that much worse than several other states.

US State Covid Cumulative Case Rates, Nov. 20 2020
and percent who usually wore a mask, Sept 2020.

Figure 8: Covid rates, Nov. 20, 2020, and percent who reported wearing a mask by state

Figure 9: Centered segmented bar chart of categories of math proficiency among 8th graders in 2011

4.2 Scatter Plots

Another popular type of glyph is the scatter plot. This panel description requests a plot type of “scatdot”. When displaying bivariate data, micromapST needs twice as much information: two variables to plot and two axis labels. We also request a robust fitted line, a new package feature, to the scatter plot by using the “parms” statement. Any option for a plotted line in R can be specified here – we ask for a heavy, dark red LOWESS smoothed line. In the function call, you see a new parameter “bordGrp”, which is used to specify a micromap boundary file other than US states. This example plots the percent of residents with a bachelor’s degree versus the percent who are living in poverty by county in Maryland.

```
###
panel_desc_MD_poved <- data.frame(
  type = c("mapcum", "id", "scatdot"),
  lab1 = c("", "", "% College by % Pov"),
  col1 = c(NA, NA, "PctBachDegree"),
  col2 = c(NA, NA, "PctLess150Pov"),
  lab3 = c(NA, NA, "% college"),
  lab4 = c(NA, NA, "% poverty"),
  parm = I(list(NA, NA,
    list(line = "LOWESS", line.col = "dark red", line.lwd = 1.75)))
)
micromapST( statsDFrame = MD_pov_ed,
  panelDesc = panel_desc_MD_poved, rowNames = "id",
  sortVar = "PctBachDegree", ascend = FALSE,
  plotNames = "full",
  bordGrp = "MarylandBG",
  title = c("Maryland counties: % Living < 150% of Poverty Level and % with 4+ Years of
  College")
)
###
Maryland counties: % Living < 150% of Poverty Level and % with 4+ Years of College
```


Figure 10: Scatter plot of poverty and college education by county in Maryland

The results are shown in Figure 10. One design feature to note in the scatter plot is that there is only a single plot for each perceptual group of counties and that scatter plot is repeated for every perceptual group. However, only the 5 counties in a perceptual group are shaded in color; the rest of the dots are open gray circles. In this way, you get the context of the dot values in each perceptual group.

The LOWESS line shows a decline in poverty with increasing college education up to a point, then it levels off. The maps show definite geographic clustering, with the highest education/lowest poverty levels in central Maryland, between Washington DC and Baltimore).

5. Using Your Own Boundary Files in micromapST

The set of Maryland county boundaries is not the only non-US state boundaries included in micromapST. Also included are National Cancer Institute cancer registry areas, several other states by county, and other international boundaries. A recently-added feature is the ability to read in your own boundary file to create the micromap. Building your own border group (boundary file) is not for the beginning R coder - there is an entire chapter in our forthcoming book that describes how to do this.

We will illustrate the process by aggregating Kentucky's 120 counties, many with sparse populations, into 15 Area Development Districts (ADDs) that are used for programs and reports within the Commonwealth of Kentucky (<https://www.kcadd.org/area-development-districts-1>). Here are the steps required to create aggregated, smoothed ADD boundaries:

- First read in your boundary file – we started with Kentucky county boundaries in a SHP file from the Census Bureau.
- We aggregated counties by using a crosswalk table to assign each county to an Area Development District, then aggregated polygons to create a new ADD border group. These steps were done in R outside the micromapST package.
- The Build Border Group function within the package will smooth the new ADD boundaries and produce a boundary file usable in linked micromaps. You can experiment with the level of smoothing to create a map where borders don't overwhelm the interior color shading but the areas are still recognizable.
- Then you specify this new border group in the micromapST call function, as we did for the last Maryland example. Figure 11 illustrates the input and output of this process.

This can be complicated, especially if you are aggregating areas first, as we did, but the process only needs to be done once, then the resulting file can be used repeatedly in micromapST.

Figure 11 Kentucky counties(left) and Kentucky Area Development District boundaries created by micromapST (right)

6. Conclusions

The micromapST R package provides quick, publication-quality linked micromap plots with many glyphs and layout options to tailor the graphic. The linked micromap design is an excellent tool for the exploration and communication of geospatial data. The recent addition of the ability to read in SHP files expands the use of LMMs for boundaries beyond US states.

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